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STUDENT'S ATTITUDE TOWARD SINGLE PARENTING AND IT'S RELATION TO THEIR EDUCATIONAL PERFORMANCE IN SELECT SCHOOLS IN MINDORO

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The study on the Student's Attitude Toward Single Parenting and its Relation to their Educational Performance in Selected Schools in Mindoro was conducted to determine the effects of having solo parents and if there is a direct relationship to the student's educational performance. Single parenting is one of the challenging roles of a parent. Providing basic needs to giving full support and attention to your children are some of the primary responsibilities of parenting. Nowadays, many families turn to broken homes due to different factors like different ideologies, third parties, the incapacity of one party to provide for the needs of the other, and vice versa. The couple who separates ways thought that separating is more helpful to their children instead of continuing but still fighting causing trauma to the children. The study was conducted on selected schools in Occidental Mindoro province. The study will utilize a descriptive research design to identify the respondents' perceptions of single parenting. The Researcher used a researcher-made questionnaire checklist to obtain data from the respondent. The questionnaire checklist also comprises questions about as sex, age, grade level, general weighted average, and family structure. The study's respondents were selected students from Division of Occidental Mindoro who are children of solo parents.

The research result shows that, single parenting does not affect their academic performance, with an overall mean of 1.53 with verbal interpretation of "disagree". Family financial status with an average mean of 1.57, exposes that parents do not put extra effort into providing for the needs of their children financially and emotionally. Some parents cannot provide enough financial support because of unstable work situations or no work at all, while some have other families where their incomes go instead of dividing it among children. Responses under moral support imply that the respondents disagree with the statements with an overall mean of 1.56 with verbal interpretations of "disagree". Solo parent neglects their moral responsibilities to their children since they are more focused on how they will earn a living. Some are not well educated about the moral issues and concerns of their child, which sometimes results to repeated nagging over their children.

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